

EMPOWERING FUTURE CHANGEMAKERS IN UZBEKISTAN: SUSTAINABILITY EDUCATION FOR GREEN BUSINESS INNOVATION

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Abstract. *This article aims to explore how sustainability education can inspire students – future leaders and entrepreneurs to become agents of green business transformation, and the role of education in shaping sustainability competencies.*

Keywords: *Sustainability, Sustainable development, education, skills, integrating sustainability studies into curricula, key competencies*

According to Air Quality index in Tashkent [IQAir, n.d.], which is ‘moderate’ 98 with the main pollutant PM10 at the moment of writing this article, but is raising a lot of concerns at times when indicator is ‘high’, the need of transitioning to green business innovation, which includes “the development and implementation of new products, services, processes, and business models” enhancing sustainability and ecological efficiency alongside with bringing social and economic value via following the sustainable methods from ‘design and production to recycling and commercialization’ [Pattison et al., 2023], and responsible entrepreneurship committed to making a choice towards ‘positive outcomes for society, the environment, and stakeholders’ by focusing on sustainable innovation and ethical conduct [Snyder, 2008b].

While 193 United Nations Member States agreed to follow the established 17 SDGs in 2015 for building a more just, sustainable and equitable world, and Uzbekistan being one of them, with the public awareness about climate change growing in times of the country adopting a Green Economy Transition Strategy (2019-2030) and a National Strategy and Roadmap to empower youth in climate action [Online Service Group, 2023b]. It is hard not to estimate the power of education, particularly in tertiary education, at times when job-ready graduates are not the only aim, but bringing up responsible, future-oriented global citizens adapting to the current challenges and striving to solve issues with innovative approach for preserving the community, region and planet (Sustainable Development Goals, n.d.). Integrating sustainability studies into curricula for various disciplines particularly business, economics and engineering, is the demand of time for educating skilled and sustainability-literate workforce capable of leading in sectors as water management, sustainable agriculture, eco-tourism, waste management, green finance and clean energy.

According to OpenAI (2023), there are 10 out of 222 higher education institutions (HEIs), which offer courses/programs/degrees in Sustainability, Green Business and Environmental Studies: Central Asian University of Environmental and Climate Change Studies (Green University), Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature (TSUULL), Erasmus Centre of Excellence in Sustainable Business and Finance, Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE), Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies (TSUOS), Samarkand International University of Technology (SIUT), Tashkent State University of Law (TSUL),

Tashkent University of Information Technologies (TUIT), Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT).

This data has its limitations, as some of the listed institutions offer degrees, some programs and some courses, as many of these programs are new, data on the numbers of students taking the courses and benefiting from them is limited. Also, two universities where Sustainability courses are taught in HEIs in Uzbekistan are not mentioned: Team University¹ and Webster University in Tashkent². Realizing that the data about the Sustainability studies is not fully reflected and a more thorough research is needed, Sustainability is a relatively new concept and the shortage of faculty and facilities is assumed and a further research is needed.

Sustainability education is designed to cultivate key competencies such as anticipatory planning, systems thinking, critical thinking, collaboration and ethical decision-making. According to WIEK et.al. (2011), these competencies enable individuals to understand complex socio-environmental challenges and take meaningful action. These skills promote the development of environmentally and socially conscious enterprises when they are applied in the context of business and entrepreneurship.

As Uzbekistan faces pressing sustainability challenges, including water scarcity, land degradation, air pollution and energy inefficiency, it aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 35% by 2030, increase energy efficiency in residential and industrial sectors and increase the share of renewable energy in electricity production. Climate-related financing and partnerships with international development institutions are gaining momentum, such as World Bank, UNDP, ADB and etc. However, the success of these policies depends heavily on human capital – a workforce that understands sustainability, can work across discipline and innovate solutions. Unfortunately, many graduates in Uzbekistan currently lack exposure to sustainability concepts, green entrepreneurship and ESG frameworks. It is necessary for the education sector to evolve to become a core pillar of the green economy transition with sustainability integrated across disciplines. Faculty development, curriculum reform and industry collaboration are still limited. Higher education institutions in Uzbekistan have to adopt a more systematic and interdisciplinary approach to sustainability education with the following key strategies:

- Policy Alignment by setting national standards and accreditation requirements that include sustainability competencies as part of graduate outcomes;
- Curriculum integration with embed sustainability principles across all faculties not being limited to natural sciences, but also in economics, engineering, business, social sciences and law and offering mandatory courses on sustainability development, green business models and climate change mitigation;
- Faculty training and incentives to enable lecturers to teach sustainability concepts effectively and incentivize interdisciplinary research and course co-design around SDGs and ESG goals;
- Experiential learning incorporating hackathons, startup incubators and innovation labs;
- Collaborations of universities with industries will provide practical exposure and employment pathways for graduates while encouraging partnerships between universities

¹ Several courses at Team University partly or fully include Sustainability studies, as Contemporary Global Issues, Theory and Practice of Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial mindset.

² Several courses at Webster University in Tashkent, as a part of the Global Citizenship Program, like Introduction into Sustainability, Environmental Ethics and Decision Making and etc.

and businesses working in sustainable agriculture, circular economy, renewable energy and environmental services.

Uzbekistan stands at a unique crossroads, as it is striving to achieve both economic modernization and environmental resilience. To realize its green economy goals, Uzbekistan should raise a new generation of leaders and green business innovators with responsible entrepreneurial skills and ethical grounding for building sustainable enterprises. By reforming higher education to include sustainability into curricula and policy alignment, Uzbekistan can empower the graduates to become future changemakers capable of creating businesses and policies, which are inclusive, profitable and regenerative.

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